

ARCHITECTURAL MONUMENTS OF THE SHEIBANID DYNASTY, THEIR ARCHITECTURE AND SIGNIFICANCE

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Abstract: *The article tells about the architectural structures built during the Sheibanid dynasty, who ruled in Transoxiana in the sixteenth century, about their architecture and significance today. You may know that the structures built during the time of the Sheibanids are of great historical importance today.*

Keywords: *Sheibanids, architecture, madrasah, mosque, Khanaka, patterns.*

We know that since time immemorial in Central Asia, that is, on our territory, the architectural and construction business has developed at a high level. We can also see this in the example of the Sheibanid dynasty, which ruled in Transoxiana during the sixteenth century. Under the rulers of Shaibani, who made a huge contribution to the development of Uzbek statehood, several structures were erected in the field of architecture.

The political events that led to the crisis of Timurid rule in the XV-XVI centuries and the establishment of the Sheibanid dynasty in Transoxiana did not affect the development of local architecture of that time and its traditions that developed in the "Navoi period". In Samarkand, during the first thirty years of the sixteenth century, that is, before the transfer of the capital to Bukhara, a lot of construction work was carried out, and many luxurious buildings were built in the city. A new settlement (Nav) has appeared in the eastern part of the suburb. The gardens of the Samarkand nobility were located here, among which Dili Afruz Park was especially famous for its beauty. Of the many structures built during this period, only a large irrigation structure-a water distributor in Zarafshan (1502) has survived to this day. This watershed divided the waters of Zarafshan into the main channel-Karadarya and Okdarya. The strength of the watershed, the ability of rivers to withstand centuries-old severe floods is evidence of the high engineering art of Uzbek masters.[1].

Architectural structures were erected not only by representatives of the ruling dynasty, but also by private owners. In many cities of the country, such as Bukhara, Samarkand, Tashkent, Karshi, Karshi, Turkestan, Merv,

Balkh, Herat, Khiva, various architectural structures were built, such as madrassas and mosques, khanaks, mosques, minarets, baths, caravanserais, cisterns, bridges and much more. The walls of the cities were repaired. For example, madrasas associated with the names of Haniyah, Abu Said and Kulbabo Kukeldash, built by Sheibanikhan in Samarkand, watershed near Samarkand, repair of the city wall in Bukhara, madrasah Mir Arab, Abdullahan, Modarihan, madrasah Barokhan and Kukeldash in Tashkent, Shaibanikhan Mosque in Turkestan, Kasim Sheikh Mosque in Karman, repair of the fortress wall in Balkhe, Abdullahan, kulbobo Kukaldash madrasah, Kukeldash madrasah in Herat. [2].

We can see that during the time of the Sheibanids there was a lot of construction work in the field of architecture. Below we will briefly focus on these architectural monuments.

The Oliy Khaniyah madrasah. To the north of Registan, construction began during the Sheibanids. After Muhammad Sheibanikhan died in 1510 in a battle with the Iranian Safavids near Merv, his decapitated body was transported to Samarkand and buried in the courtyard of the madrasah on a high pedestal of gray marble. The construction of the building was continued by his son Timur Muhammad Sultan. He died in 1514. The construction of the madrasah was completed by his wife Mer Sultanhanim. By his decree, a Khaniyah madrasah will be built on the north side of the Oliyad Khaniyah Madrasah, which will have the same luxury as this madrasah. These two madrasahs combined stucco and gilded mosaics. Descendants of Samarkand Sheibanids are buried in a hut in Madaras. In the XVIII century, both madrassas were demolished. By the end of the eighteenth century, the Oliyad Khaniyah madrasah was partially restored. But in 1874, the building was demolished, and the hut was moved to another place so that it could cross the street from here.[3].

Cook kupbaz madrasah. It was built around the middle of the XVI century on the south side of Registan Square. This madrasah was built by Kuckinchihan's son Abu Saidhan. The madrasah contained a domed hall of the Samarkand saga of the Sheibanids. The name of the madrasah "blue dome" indicates that the blue dome of the Sagan madrasah played a key role. The underground remains of the walls of the main window were preserved until the beginning of the XX century under the name "Childukhtaron". Beautifully carved and carved inscriptions on tombstones indicate that Lovecraft, his 3 sons and 3 grandchildren were buried here. Among them is Abu Saidhan, who built this madrasah. His tombstone is carved from gray-black stone and decorated with magnificent carvings. Due to the proximity of the stone material and the method of its processing to the tombstones of the Timurids in Herat, it is believed that one of those

brilliant craftsmen from Herat was involved in the manufacture of tombstones.[4].

The world is an Arab madrasah. An architectural monument in Bukhara, built by Sheikh Abdullah in 1530-1536 with funds donated by the Bukhara Khan Ubaydullahan. The total area of the madrasah is 68.5 x 51.8 m, the courtyard is 35.4 x 31.3 m, the darshana is 8x8 m. The courtyard has the shape of a rectangle and is surrounded by 114 huts with two niches. The patio-terrace with 4 high roofs between the sides gives the courtyard a monumentality. In terms of structure, the original appearance of the patterned Southern roof has been preserved, star-shaped ornaments are found in the composition of these patterns. According to some preserved fragments of ornaments on it, you can find out that the patterns were extremely elegant and refined. According to legends, the base of the madrasah was deepened and reinforced with mountain stones, wells were made to drain snow and rain water, through which water was discharged outside the city fortifications. The Mir Arab Madrasah embodies traditional projects and ideas typical of Central Asian religious schools. In connection with the 2500 anniversary of Bukhara, relief patterns and inscriptions were restored on the facades and domes of the madrasah; Currently, students study Islam at the madrasah.[5].

Kush Madrasah In Bukhara. These madrasahs are located in Guzar kush madrasah. Madrasahs were built opposite each other. The madrasah located on the western side is called Abdullah's western Madrasah, while the madrasah located on the eastern side is called Abdullah's Eastern Madrasah or Modarikhan Madrasah (often called Modarikhan Madrasah) because it was built by his mother. The Western madrasah was built by the famous representative of the rulers of Sheibani, Abdullahan ibn Iskandarkhan ibn Janibek Khan ibn Abulhair Khan. Its construction was admirably appreciated by Hafiz Ibn Bukhari. It was the highest and richest higher educational institution of the madrasah era. His financial support was provided at the expense of the fund's property allocated to him. The madrasah also had a rich library. The library contained many fundamental books on tariqa, wisdom, logic, nahwa, tafsir, hadith and other fields of science. Among them were the works of such great thinkers as Mahmoud az-Zamakhshari, Imam Gazzali.[6]

Of the monuments of civil architecture of the Sheibanid period, in addition to bridges and cisterns, five buildings with patterns built at the intersections of the bazaar streets of Bukhara deserve special attention. These are buildings: Sarofon currents, Telpakfurushon currents, Zarafshan currents and those that have not reached us, Tirgdan currents and Urufurushon currents. This type of luxury buildings, along with a large covered market on top of a hill named Abdullahan, formed the central part

of the capital as the external architectural appearance of the always crowded market. Of the works of civil architecture, it has functioned very well so far. You can show a sundress bath. In the decoration of architectural buildings in Bukhara, both inside and outside, various methods were used, but glazed carved mosaic, consisting of mosaics of different colors, specially built according to the finished drawing, was used much less often in the XVI century, as an expensive and time-consuming method. The relief of the pattern, its parts were given golden water, the background was painted blue or green, and small flowers and patterns were painted accordingly. All this created the illusion that golden patterns were scattered on a green or blue field with a small-flowered ornament. The patterns on the stone are known from the magnificent tombstones made of gray marble stored in the Bukhara Museum. These stones are very well crafted from head to toe and are covered with carefully carved floral ornaments, as well as engraved inscriptions that strictly follow the rules of calligraphy.[7].

Although there was no such construction under the Sheibanids as under the Timurids, during the sixteenth century the field of architecture did not stand still. During this period, major construction works were carried out not only in Bukhara and Samarkand, but also in other cities. The memorial monuments erected during this period by talented masters of Uzbek architecture further enrich our history.

Summing up, we can say that every city in Uzbekistan has a beautiful appearance, memorial monuments erected during that period have a special significance. Many of these madrasahs, built with high taste for their time, were restored after independence, and Juna retained the same splendor as before. We must insist that the architectural monuments of the Sheibanid period are one of the highest examples of architectural art in Uzbekistan.

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